

Rights for Time Working Paper

Temporalities in Diasporic Voices: Past, Present and Future in Narratives of Armenians in Lebanon

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Originally drafted 29 August 2022 | Revised 27 February 2024

Introduction

Over the years, Lebanon has accepted multiple waves of refugees, fleeing wars, conflicts, persecution and violence of various types in neighboring countries or the wider region. A vast corpus of literature has been produced to study a wide range of aspects related to these refugee inflows and presence. Some have focused on one refugee “group,” while others have adopted more comparative analyses of different groups – either from a more “macroscopic” perspective without offering a detailed account of each,¹ or through more in-depth analyses of cases mostly from a macro, governance perspective,² though the micro level of people’s narratives or experiences has also been researched (Chatty).³ While many of these studies have tackled time-related issues, explicitly or implicitly, they have not done so systematically or in an in-depth manner, because their central focus or goal has not often been to study temporality. In addition, while the concept of time has been addressed in many of these works, the focus of studies on temporalities in relation to refugee studies in Lebanon has been on relatively more recent displacement cases, particularly those of Syrians and, to a lesser extent, Palestinians.⁴ Focusing on groups that have a longer presence (that is, whose ancestors have arrived earlier) in Lebanon could help provide a more *historicized* account or analysis of temporality in refugee studies in the country. This paper attempts to do so by shedding light on the case of Armenians in Lebanon, adopting specifically a temporal lens with a more micro-oriented focus.

Such historicization of temporality analysis could provide valuable lessons for scholarly researchers, policymakers, humanitarian actors, and refugee/community organizations or leaders with regard to more recent refugee waves. It could, for example, inform commemorative activities that deal with the past, community organization efforts that focus on the present, and planning of policies and programs that are more future-oriented (related to education, urban planning development, or other fields, for example). Such historicization is particularly important in the case of Lebanon, given the multiple waves of displacement cases the country has experienced, as mentioned above, and taking into consideration the protracted nature of some of them.

¹ Filippo Dionigi, 2017, Statehood and Refugees: Patterns of Integration and Segregation of Refugee Populations in Lebanon from a Comparative Perspective, *Middle East Law and Governance*, Vol. 9, (pp. 113-146), p. 115.

² Nora Stel, 2021, *Hybrid Political Order and the Politics of Uncertainty: Refugee Governance in Lebanon*, London and New York: Routledge.

³ Dawn Chatty, 2010, *Displacement and Dispossession in the Modern Middle East*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

⁴ Nanor Karageozian, 2024, Time in Studies of Displacement in Lebanon: Review of Selected Literature, *Rights for Time Working Paper*, forthcoming.

Brief background of Armenian case

One of the first refugee waves in Lebanon's modern history, occurring mostly in the decades prior to the country's independence in 1943, has been the arrival of Armenians in the first half of the 20th century.⁵ Armenians fled the mass persecution and genocide they faced within the Ottoman Empire mostly during World War I and in the Republic of Turkey during the first couple of decades after its establishment, as well as the instability of other neighboring countries, including most recently in Iraq and Syria.

Multiple studies exist examining the different aspects of Armenian presence in Lebanon, including the evolution of unorganized masses of refugees into a well-established diasporic community, which has maintained its distinctiveness and links to its roots and identity, while being relatively well-integrated into Lebanese social, economic and political life. In a short essay, Antranig Dakessian (2019) provides a very brief history of Armenians in Lebanon.⁶ Armenians' integration into Lebanon's social, economic and political context has been examined in works by Nicola Migliorino (2008)⁷ and Tsolin Nalbantian (2018; 2020).⁸ Different topics related to the Armenians of Lebanon are addressed in various chapters of a conference proceedings volume edited by Aida Boudjikianian (2009).⁹ The experience of displacement and dispossession of various ethnoreligious groups in Middle Eastern countries, including Armenians in Lebanon, is the focus of Dawn Chatty's (2010) book.¹⁰ There is also an older brief overview by Richard G. Hovannisian (1974) of Armenian presence in Lebanon, as well as other countries of the Middle East.¹¹ More recently, a report has been published to present the findings of a public opinion survey in Lebanon (in addition to Armenian diasporic communities in other countries).¹² Many other studies exist examining different other aspects of Armenian life in Lebanon.

Time is referred or alluded to in different ways, implicitly or explicitly, in many of these studies. In this paper, I shed light on how some temporal concepts are manifested in the narratives of individual Armenians in Lebanon – for many of them, decades after their ancestors arrived in Lebanon as refugees; or, for others, following their or their parents' more recent move to Lebanon from other countries in the region that have experienced wars or other types of tension, mainly Iraq and Syria. More specifically, the paper focuses on the temporal variable of past, present and future¹³ in these narratives.

⁵ Though Armenians have been present in Lebanon even before the 20th century.

⁶ Antranig Dakessian, 2019, [Lebanon](#), Armenian Diaspora Survey.

⁷ Nicola Migliorino, 2008, *(Re)constructing Armenia in Lebanon and Syria: Ethno-cultural Diversity and the State in the Aftermath of a Refugee Crisis*, New York, N.Y.; Oxford: Berghahn Books.

⁸ Tsolin Nalbantian, 2018, Armenians in Lebanon: Becoming Local in the Levant, *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, Vol. 50, No. 4, pp. 773-777; Tsolin Nalbantian, 2020, *Armenians Beyond Diaspora: Making Lebanon their Own*, Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.

⁹ Aida Boudjikianian, ed., 2009, [Armenians of Lebanon: From Past Princesses and Refugees to Present-Day Community](#), Beirut: Haigazian University Press.

¹⁰ Chatty, 2010.

¹¹ Richard G. Hovannisian, 1974, The Ebb and Flow of the Armenian Minority in the Arab Middle East, *Middle East Journal*, Vol. 28, No. 1, pp. 19-32.

¹² Hratch Tchilingirian, ed., 2019, [Armenian Diaspora Public Opinion \(1\): Armenian Diaspora Survey](#), London: Armenian Institute. The data analyzed in this paper was collected as part of this survey, as explained in the "Methodology" section below.

¹³ This variable, along with others – such as timing, sequence, frequency (or rhythm), (a)synchronization, speed, and duration – are identified and elaborated upon in relation to refugee studies in a separate paper prepared within the framework of the [Rights for Time project](#): Nanor Karageozian, forthcoming, Time in Refugee Studies: A Conceptual Literature Review from a Social Theory Lens.

The Armenian case is interesting from the perspective of providing a historicized approach to the study of temporality in refugee studies in Lebanon for a number of reasons. One reason is the *longue durée* that characterizes diasporic existence and experience,¹⁴ such as that of Armenians, especially when the focus is on a “victim” diaspora¹⁵ like the Armenian, for the development of which refugeeness has played a central role. Another reason why the Armenian case is interesting from a historicization perspective is because, despite its *longue durée*, the community has also received newer refugee waves from Iraq and mainly Syria in more recent years, thus allowing for some comparative analysis.

Methodology

The paper relies on over 30 interviews, consisting of open-ended questions, with Armenians of different backgrounds residing in Lebanon that I conducted as part of the [Armenian Diaspora Survey](#) (ADS)’s qualitative component in 2019.¹⁶ The interviews covered the following main topics: identity (including self-identification and issues related mainly to language, religion, church and mixed marriages); political engagement (both Armenian community/diaspora politics and national/local politics in Lebanon); community engagement; and connections with Armenia, Artsakh and diasporic communities elsewhere. Thus, the goal of the research project and hence the main focus of the interviews was not temporality. Nevertheless, time manifested in different ways in the interviews, allowing me to analyze these narratives specifically from a temporal perspective, as demonstrated in the next section of this paper.

Of the 32 interviews that I conducted, 10 were held in October 2019, before the civil uprising and ongoing economic crisis started in Lebanon, and the rest between November and December 2019. Interviewees with diverse backgrounds – in terms of gender, age, generation, education level, occupation, political affiliation, religious denomination, place of residence, community engagement, etc. – were selected. Selection occurred through a snowball method, taking into consideration different “entry points.” More specifically, interviewees included 17 males and 15 females. Out of the 32 interviewees, 11 were between the ages of 16 and 30, another 11 were between 31 and 50, and 10 were 50 and above. Regarding generation or immigration wave, 9 interviewees were first generation in the country (they were born outside of Lebanon); 13 were second generation in the country (they were born in the country but at least one of their parents was born outside of the country); and 10 were third or more generation in the country (both of their parents were born in the country). From an educational background perspective, 21 of the interviewees had higher education, while the rest had not attained higher education. In terms of Armenian community engagement, 15 reported being engaged in some degree or way and 17 were reportedly not engaged. With regard to the interviewees’ places of residence, the breakdown was as follows:

- Beirut Governorate/Greater Beirut area and various areas of Mount Lebanon (besides Byblos and Batroun): 20
- Byblos (Jbeil) and the nearby city of Batroun (Mount Lebanon Governorate): 3 (2 and 1, respectively)

¹⁴ Michel Bruneau, 2010, “Diasporas, Transnational Spaces and Communities”, in Rainer Bauböck and Thomas Faist (eds.), *Diaspora and Transnationalism: Concepts, Theories and Methods*. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press, (pp. 35-49), pp. 37, 47.

¹⁵ Robin Cohen, 1997, *Global Diasporas: An Introduction*, London: UCL Press.

¹⁶ ADS is a multiyear public opinion research project, with quantitative and qualitative components, in Armenian diaspora communities in different countries about various issues, attitudes and trends shaping these communities. In 2019, the project covered Lebanon, Canada, Argentina and Romania. The project is funded by the Armenian Communities Department of the Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation and carried out under the auspices of the Armenian Institute in London.

- Bekaa Governorate: 7 (including 1 from Zahle, 1 from Ablah village [near Zahle], 1 from Jalala [between Zahle and Chtaura], and 4 from Anjar)
- Tripoli: 2

To protect the interviewees' anonymity, no names are mentioned in this paper. I have instead identified interviewees by number, based on the order in which interviews were conducted, with P1 (participant 1) having been interviewed first.

It is important to understand the context within which the ADS interviews were conducted. In this regard, it must be emphasized that the interviews took place in a wider context of declining Armenian diasporic communities in the Middle East, mostly as a result of the Iraq and Syria wars in the last few decades. The region has been characterized by various population movements, including of Armenians, who have either migrated to Europe or North America, or to other countries, whether in the region or elsewhere. The largest such population movement has been that of Syrians, including of Armenians from Syria, a large number of whom have fled Syria to find temporary or permanent refuge in various regions of Lebanon, in Armenia, or other countries. In addition, since mid-October 2019, Lebanon has been facing an acute economic crisis, political instability, and security incidences – compounded by the COVID-19 pandemic, the Beirut port explosion of 4 August 2020, and other related crises – all of which have also influenced the Lebanese-Armenian community, among others. Most of the ADS interviews were conducted after the onset of these recent, ongoing crises, though at their early phases. From an Armenia context perspective, the research was undertaken after the 2018 regime change in Armenia, but before the 2020 44-day Nagorno-Karabakh (Artsakh) war.

Past, present and future as manifested in narratives of Armenians in Lebanon

1) Impact of past events on identity formation, evolution and transmission

One aspect of how the past is manifested in narratives of Armenians from Lebanon I interviewed is their reference to specific past events in the history of the Armenian people in general as key historical moments that have affected or shaped their present identity. Two such historical events are the Armenian Genocide and the independence of the Republic of Armenia in 1991 (with the break-up of the Soviet Union).

For example, one interviewee (P19) explained how her connection to Lebanon and Armenia, and hence her identity, have changed since Armenia's independence; now that Armenia is independent, she has the peace of mind to identify as Lebanese-Armenian, and sometimes feels even a stronger bond with Lebanese people compared to *hayasdantsis* (Armenians from Armenia).

Before Armenia's independence, my feelings were different. After independence, it is completely different for me. Now I have a sort of sense of emotional comfort. ... For me, now, being Lebanese and being Armenian are equal things. And I even go as far as saying that I am more like Lebanese today than the Armenian who lives in Armenia. ... Before [independence], for example, when I used to hear that in Syria or Iraq or anywhere else an Armenian school was closed or something had happened to a church, I used to feel sadness in my heart, an unbearable [feeling]. Now, the first thing I say is that I don't care, let them go to Armenia.

Others referred to some specific past events or developments in their personal lives as key turning points that have affected the evolution of their identity over time. For example, one interviewee (P3) explained that her identity has changed over the years, and her current mixed identity was formed especially when she went from an Armenian school – a “closed society” as she called it – to a Lebanese public one (after

grade 9), where she had to interact with students from various sects. There, she felt the need, the obligation, to present Armenian history and roots (e.g. the Genocide) to classmates and people around her. Another interviewee (P19) described that for the first 15 years of his life, he did not feel Armenian at all and had no knowledge about anything Armenian. He grew up in an environment where there were no Armenians except for other members of his family. He felt Lebanese. But then because of the bullying/discrimination he experienced by people who kept calling him “the Armenian” (“*el Arman*”, because of his last name that ends in -ian), he started researching online, reading, following news on Armenia. It is then that he started feeling that even though he lives in Lebanon and feels he belongs to the country, he does have a sort of attachment to another country, Armenia.

Another aspect of how the past surfaces as a key factor in the shaping of identity is through perceptions of the Armenian people’s will and ability to endure and survive over time despite enormous hardships faced by different past generations. Many interviewees argued that thanks to their persevering and survivor spirit, as they described, Armenians have not only successfully overcome difficulties that they have faced as refugees after arriving in Lebanon and rebuilt their personal and family lives but have also flourished as a community and generally contributed to the country’s development. One interviewee (P11) explained:

Having survived the Genocide and still smiling ... or still finding something to celebrate. It makes you different. And yeah, I’m gonna brag about it. ... It is a very tragic thing, yet we survived it. Actually, our ancestors did. So, the fact that they did and the fact that everywhere we go we have a certain reputation of not being immigrants, more like we actually own up, and we integrate... There is no pity. We are independent.

Another interviewee (P8) described how he explains this past journey to non-Armenian Lebanese he often meets, mostly in his workplace:

I say ... we came and were very helpful to you and the city [he probably means the country] and we taught you [non-Armenian Lebanese] a lot of crafts, the city [again, he probably means the country] got developed more. They do not accept that. They say, “no, you came barefoot, and we looked after you.” I try to convince them again that their perception is wrong. We are a working race [or people], we are a creating race [or people].¹⁷

Some interviewees linked these experiences of past generations of Armenians in Lebanon and the transformation these generations experienced to their ability to build new towns (e.g. Bourj Hammoud, Anjar) in the country. For example, an 86-year-old interviewee (P25) recounted the difficulties Armenians faced when they first arrived in Anjar, in the Bekaa Valley; it was a place full of diseases that Armenians helped transform into quite a developed and self-sustaining village, he explained.

Some interviewees (P6, P10, P14) linked this past journey to the need or sense of obligation to preserve their Armenian identity in the present; they feel they need to presently maintain their Armenianness as a duty towards previous generations that had endured hardships. For example, one interviewee (P27) compared the difficulties faced by her grandparents during the Genocide with how her son does not know Armenian fluently (he went to a non-Armenian school), does not feel Armenian (at least in the same way she does), is distanced from the Armenian community, and does not know much/is not interested in Armenian history and issues. She thought that this is very unfortunate given the sacrifices and struggles her grandmother (a Genocide survivor) and her parents had to go through to keep their identity and

¹⁷ He uses the Armenian word *tsegh*, which translates into race.

transmit it to herself, in a way implying that her son is not doing enough to respect the efforts of the past generations.

Somehow related to this point was the view among some interviewees that Armenians should feel proud and should inform others and future generations about their uniqueness. As P14 said, this entails a sense of obligation to transmit Armenian history, culture, language to others and to future generations, in order to preserve them. This sense of obligation stems partly from the fact that Armenians have endured a lot of hardships in the past and have made a lot of sacrifices throughout history.

In the end, each one of us has a duty, as an Armenian, and if we feel Armenian, to disseminate this culture, to talk about this culture ... And it is an obligation for us to transmit it to others and to future generations. ... Because if we don't do it, no one else will do. ... And if we don't do it, it will disappear. ... When people have died for us to remain Armenian, I do not have the permission [or right] to think twice about this issue. ... For sure I should feel a duty. When I learn the history and I see the kind of hardships that Armenians have passed through, no, I cannot be a different kind of Armenian. In general, if I am an indifferent Armenian today, the entire history would have no meaning. So, wherever I am in my surroundings, I try to share, work, talk, so that the sacrifices that they [past generations] have made, whether financial or with their lives, are not in vain at the end.

2) Memory and/or experience of historic Armenia: (Spatio)temporal journeys to ancestral lands

Another way the past surfaces in narratives of Armenians from Lebanon is through their memory of (or actually what they have heard from previous generations about) and/or actual encounters with their ancestral lands. The latter are especially interesting spatiotemporal journeys filled with mixed emotions of joy and sorrow/anger (P12, P16, P23, P25). When describing these experiences, many of the interviewees made spatiotemporal comparisons. They often described these lands' importance as places with physical traces of Armenian existence or culture (Armenian churches, neighborhoods, houses) but of course lack of Armenian people, unlike in the past (P25, P32). They sometimes described how different these places are compared to how they currently live (P16). They also mentioned the presently abandoned, destructed or transformed nature of these places. The parallels that one interviewee (P32) drew between some things she saw during her visit to Cilicia¹⁸ and Aleppo (where she was born and raised before recently moving to Lebanon due to the war in Syria) are interesting; she highlighted the similarities of architectural elements as well as the destiny of destruction between the two places.

The windows [of the previous Armenian-owned houses in Ayntab, a town in Cilicia] have the shape of crosses and the door clock has the shape of a cross. That's how you know they are Armenian houses. ... And I remember very well that in Nor Kyugh [an Armenian neighborhood in Aleppo], the houses, those with courtyards, were built exactly that way. ... In Nor Kyugh, when I was little, [I remember] the door clocks had the shape of crosses. And the windows (each room used to have a window that would remain open for the air to circulate) were cross-shaped. ... And that has of course come to Aleppo from Historic Armenia. ... Of course, it [the visit in Cilicia] was very tragic for us. The church in Urfa [another town in Cilicia] had been transformed into a mosque. ... We entered. ... I imagined for a moment what we would do if the churches in Aleppo became like that one day. This was in 2010, when we went [to Cilicia]. We did not know that after just two–three

¹⁸ A region in the southeastern coast of present-day Turkey, which was highly populated by Armenians before the Genocide. After the end of World War I, when the region became under French control, many of its Armenian residents returned to their homes. However, they fled it again in 1921, when the region became part of the Republic of Turkey, settling mostly in nearby Middle Eastern countries, including what eventually became the Republic of Lebanon.

years, our churches [in Aleppo], especially St. Kevork Church, would become such a [destroyed or endangered] church, and I am sure one day it will no longer be ours.

For most interviewees who have very distant connections to these ancestral lands, the visits were more about the idea of having been from or having roots from there, and less about the physical place or family traces there per se. In the case of visits to Mousa Ler by those with ancestral roots from that area,¹⁹ their experiences and feelings were more immediate, closer to the present and at a personal, family level, because they usually found it easier to locate their family houses or reconnect to places attached to family memories, especially when they visited with parents/grandparents who had actual memories of these places. Again, these encounters led to comparisons with their past journeys/present situation in Lebanon. For example, one interviewee (P12) recounted his visit as follows:

We had heard about Musa Ler. We had not seen it. But when we saw it, the stories [of my parents who were born there] came to life before us and we felt that pain. We also felt their pain that they had left those places, they came to a village like Anjar, like a swamp, they suffered until they reached a certain living standard. How can I explain their feelings? ... Although they were happy [during the visit], but at the same time, they were upset. ... But we were happy that we took them there, that we saw it too; we lived there, we saw the church my grandfather had built, we saw my dad's ancestral house, we found it. These are mixed feelings that I cannot explain in words, to be honest. It is something you feel. ... Now that my parents have passed away, it makes no sense to go there without them because we have already left that place.

3) Uncertainties of the present situation and related to the future

Many of the interviewees expressed a feeling of uncertainty, whether related to their present situation and/or their future in Lebanon.

This sense of uncertainty often has a spatial dimension in terms of lack of a strong connection or sense of belonging to specific physical places – whether in general or mostly outside of Armenia. However, it also has a temporal aspect, as it raises time-related questions: Is this feeling of uncertainty just temporary or a long-term situation? Is it associated with present difficulties (especially in light of the crises in Lebanon) or is it a long-standing feeling?

For some interviewees, this lack of a strong sense of belonging to physical places, especially outside of Armenia but sometimes even towards Armenia, stemmed from the fact that they are diasporans; they always feel as strangers or guests (in the diaspora) because their ancestors were obliged to become diasporans due to external, forced reasons, namely the Genocide (e.g. P7, P8, P12, P24). So, they perceived this as a long-standing situation. Interestingly, most of these interviewees were either born or have lived parts of their lives outside of Lebanon. This feeling does not necessarily mean that such interviewees did not feel comfortable or that they have serious difficulties living in Lebanon or in different places in the diaspora. The words of one interviewee (R24), who had lived in other countries for a few years and has close family members outside of Lebanon, were indicative of this long-term nomadic feeling that is perceived to be characteristic of diasporans:

¹⁹ Musa Ler (or Musa Dagh, currently in southeastern Turkey, near the Mediterranean coast). Its Armenian residents led a successful resistance to the Genocide in 1915. After the end of the World War I, when the Sanjak of Alexandretta within which Musa Ler was located came under French control in 1918, the population of its Armenian villages returned to their homes only to flee the province again in 1939, when it was handed to Turkey. Most of them were eventually settled in the village of Anjar, Lebanon.

I was born and raised in Lebanon, the child of an Armenian family, [but] I do not feel Lebanese because the Arab tells me '*entou Arman*' [you, Armenians], that is, he sees you as a stranger. ... We have always sung about the homeland, so [homeland is supposed to be] Armenia. I have been going to Armenia for more than 21 years, [but] I am an *akhber*²⁰ in Armenia. I also have a[n Armenian] passport, I have a house, [but] I am a stranger [*odar*] to them [Armenians from Armenia], I am not a *hayasdantsi* [person/Armenian from Armenia]. I am from Musa Ler, [but] I went to Musa Ler, I felt like a stranger as well. [So,] I interpret this as follows: An Armenian lives in a tent [*vranapnag*, meaning he is like a nomadic person], that is, he carries his tent in his backpack; wherever he finds a living, he sets up the tent and stays there/becomes from that place. But he is not [really] from there. He always travels around the four corners of the world with a tent. Wherever you go, an Armenian has installed his tent, and looks towards the source of his bread. ... This is neither negative nor positive.

While many of these interviewees explained or alluded that this sense of uncertainty or liminality is a long-term situation, some also linked it to the general political and economic instability of Lebanon as well as the recent displacement that other Armenian (and/or other Christian) communities faced in the Middle East, especially the neighboring Syrian-Armenian one. For example, one interviewee (P8), who was born in Iraq, explains that he has always felt a lack of connection to a physical place outside of Armenia: "In Iraq, I used to feel that I do not belong there as an Armenian. As an Armenian in Lebanon, I feel that I am a guest in Lebanon. I know that our place is in our homeland [Armenia]. ... In the Middle East, whether in Lebanon, Iraq or Syria, we are like guests." But he also linked this to recent developments in the Middle East, denoting that this feeling of being a guest has been accentuated by these events, making him worried not only for his presence in the region but also for the future generation. "I am always worried about the future of my children, because in the Middle East, charcoal is always [ready to burn] in the fire. ... Christians are emigrating, be it from Syria or from Iraq. Tomorrow, I am afraid it will be Lebanon's turn." Similarly, P25, who lives in Anjar, explained:

I'm worried. Maybe others are just as worried as I am. ... We are proud of our Armenian town of Anjar; it is good, it is in progress ... But the situation in this country is not very clear and it is not good. And we are surrounded by neighboring villages, all of which are Muslim, and they have their eyes on our village. They do not miss a small opportunity. That is why, I have always said, and I will say now, that any Armenian, no matter where he is from, if he is going to build a house, a shop, [establish] a craft, etc., let him think about going to Armenia. The one and only salvation is our homeland, our Armenia. Whatever we build here is not ours. Eventually, one day, we have to leave this [place] and go. As it happened recently with the case of Iraq, the case of Syria. What happened to that Syrian-Armenian community, the Aleppo-Armenian community? It became scattered. Now our fate in Lebanon is uncertain and we do not know where we are going. I mean, it's worrying for me ... for years in general [it has been like this].

A large number of interviewees did not see their future in Lebanon. Some said they do not feel a sufficient connection to it and that is the main reason they do not want to continue living in Lebanon. But the desire to leave the country was also mentioned by many people who said they do feel attached to Lebanon. The main reason they mentioned is that they do not feel a sense of care on behalf of the Lebanese state/government. They do not feel that Lebanon provides stability, peace of mind, job opportunities, even basic needs (P16). Because of these issues, as well as the history of instability (including during but also following the Lebanese Civil War) and the current state of uncertainty, several interviewees said they

²⁰ Term used to refer to repatriates during the Soviet-era repatriation that continues to be used sometimes to refer to diasporans, often in a derogatory way.

do not have hope Lebanon will improve. For example, one interviewee (P28) explained that “he is Lebanese and is attached to and loves Lebanon,” but he is worried about the next generation; his children are now experiencing similar things his generation experienced as kids (such as the war) – nothing seems to have changed. This also seems to affect their engagement in local/national politics in Lebanon (e.g. P6, P10). Such narratives are in line with recent publications that reflect on situations where states affected by deteriorating socioeconomic and political instability, such as Lebanon, “no longer offer temporalities of hope,” by “severing the minimal bond of providing to their citizens’ basic needs,” as Tamirace Fakhoury (2024) describes.²¹ These situations, often lead to what Ali Ali (2023) describes as “displacement in place,” defined as “coercive processes that disrupt valued ways of living and functioning” even if people have not emigrated physically – within a context of “intentional government inertia.”²² This view of displacement diverges from common approaches that focus on displacement as “moments of departure and subsequent migration trajectories.”²³

Conclusion

This paper examines how time emerges in narratives of Armenians in Lebanon, an ethnoreligious group whose presence in the country often spans generations. It argues that temporality manifests in these narratives mainly through references to past events, the memory of or experiences of actual journeys to ancestral lands, and a sense of uncertainty related to the present and future. All of these perceptions of time – often interlinked with those of space – seem to have an impact on how Armenians identify themselves, engage in Armenian community activities, participate in socioeconomic and political life in Lebanon, experience their sense of belonging to places within and outside of Lebanon, perceive their links to past generations, wish to raise their children, and imagine their futures, among others. By focusing on the Armenian case, the paper diverges from many recent studies on displacement in Lebanon dealing with the topic of temporality, which focus mostly on Syrian and Palestinian refugees. While these displacement cases provide valuable insights on time in refugee studies in Lebanon, this paper advocates for a more historicized focus, taking the case of a diasporic group whose refugee origins largely go back more than a century. The case of Armenians in Lebanon is also interesting because despite the long presence of many of them in the country, the community has also experienced waves of more recent refugee influxes from other diasporic communities in the region, mainly Iraq and Syria, due to developments in these countries. In a country that currently hosts a large number of refugees with different backgrounds and that has experienced protracted refugee “crises,” a historicized approach may provide valuable insights to scholars, policymakers, practitioners and community actors.

²¹ Tamirace Fakhoury, 2024 (15 February), [Leaving Lebanon: A Panacea After the Financial Collapse?](#) Lebanese Center for Policy Studies.

²² Ali Ali, 2023, Displacement in Place and the Financial Crisis in Lebanon, *Journal of Refugee Studies*, Vol. 00, No. 0, (pp. 1-19), pp. 2-3.

²³ Ali, 2023, p. 8.